

An Automatic System for Elevator Monitoring

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Abstract— an elevator is a part and parcel of modern life in developed countries. The safety and reliability of an elevator system is of great importance as it carries people and other goods. During peak hours of the day, waiting long time in front of an elevator causes mental weariness. In this paper, we have hinted an automatic system that will estimate and display the free weight and volume of an elevator for the passengers using sensors and computer vision techniques. Then the passengers can make a decision and ride on their convenient elevators.

Keywords— Elevator Monitoring, Occupied Space Estimation for Elevators, IR Obstacle Sensors, and Camera based Depth Estimation.

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1 INTRODUCTION

AN elevator is a conveyor device or transport equipment that moves people or goods between floors or levels or decks of a building, vessel, or other structures. It has become a part and parcel of modern life in developed countries. The number of floors in high buildings, skyscrapers, and towers generate the usage of elevators. Many commercial skyscrapers may have at least 20-100 floors, this makes an average of more than 1000 people that would have to use the elevators. Hence during the rush hours (arrival and departure) time, at least 1000 people will have to use the elevator from the top floor to the ground floor and vice-versa. Despite the elevator gets full at the upper most floor and no more space for any other person or object to get on at any other floor, it will still have to stop at every floor where it has been called at those particular given floors yet no one can board resulting waste of time. For commercial skyscrapers this is a big problem since a lot of time will be wasted just at the elevator lounge. If it is simply assumed that each floor has at least two elevators in a thirty-floor building, people call the elevators in each floor even they are already occupied in weight and/or volume. When it is end of the daily work, thousand of home-bound people wait at each floor and call the elevator to get out of the building and go their home. However, even the elevator is occupied in weight and volume, elevator stops at each floor in case of calling by the people. This causes people in elevator stop at each floor even their elevator is over-filled by the people. This is known as an annoying problem for the people who use elevators in their daily life. The idea is to control the elevators according to their both weight and volume not to stop them if they are already over-filled in weight and volume. Weight sensors already exist in most of the elevators. But there is no utilization concept of volume sensors in the elevators. Kids wagon can take huge space even their weight is less than the limiting weight of an elevator. Except human being, some-

times some accessories or boxes can be carried by the elevators. If there is no space in the elevator, it should not stop to accept new passengers but it could give a signal to the passengers beforehand that it is unable to elevate new stuffs. Actually, the weight and volume information of elevators can be monitored for the waiting passengers and they can be guided before they call the elevator. Additionally, elevator can be analyzed with a video camera (e.g., Microsoft Kinect) mounted to the ceiling of elevator with a depth sensor next to it. By dint of video camera and depth sensor integration, we have developed a system that automatically monitors elevator and warns the new passengers about the current status of elevation. The important functionalities of our system include: (a) The threshold for volume constraint is to be parameterized by the system; (b) The system automatically estimates the necessary and sufficient parameters and then makes a decision whether the elevator is overfilled in volume; and (c) It warns the passengers if the elevator is overfilled in volume. To work reliably and efficiently, the system examines the following attributes rightfully: (i) Volumetric capacity of the elevator; (ii) Amount of occupied volume in the elevator; (iii) Amount of empty volume in the elevator; (iv) The height of the longest object in the elevator; and (v) Height of the shortest object in the elevator. We offer two design models in which the depth estimation is performed either through cameras or IR obstacle sensors. By installing two cameras next to each other, we can monitor the above attributes and estimate the necessary and sufficient parameters by calculating the stereoscopic depth information. Second method is achieved by installing IR obstacle sensors to the ceiling of the elevator in which the resolution is adjusted by parametrizing the width and height of the grid cells that sensors take place on the ceiling. In the proposed model, every single sensor measures if there exists an obstacle in pre-defined distance between the ceiling and base

of the elevator. In case of object detection, corresponding grid cell is signed as 1 (True); otherwise flagged as 0 (Zero) to employ connected component analysis in further steps. By this way, the area occupied by the passengers is calculated and a given threshold adjusts the sensitivity of the detection module.

Figure 1 depicts our proposed model. In our system, IR obstacle sensors (1) are placed on the elevator ceiling (2) and occupied area inside the elevator is calculated by microprocessor (5) which uses the information of h : perpendicular distance between the ceiling (2) and base (4) while estimating the x defined as the perpendicular distance between the ceiling (2) and passengers. Doors (3) of the proposed elevator model is also shown in the figure.

Fig. 1. Design of the Proposed Model

In the proposed scenario; based on the predefined volume and weight thresholds of a specific elevator, if either volume or weight will exceed their given thresholds and if the elevator will be called, then the elevator will not stop and give signal that it is unable to elevate new passengers.

The remaining part of this paper has been organized as follows: Section 2 accords with the most fashionable techniques; Section 3 delineates the proposed framework; Section 4 experimental set and some most likely outcomes; finally, Section 5 makes a conclusion of the work with further study.

2 STATE-OF-THE-ART METHODS

Meng et al. [1] proposed the elevator monitoring theoretical system, established the system framework, and tested the performance of this model. The design and implementation of remote elevator monitoring system based on GPRS and embedded technology were proposed by Dawei et al. [2]. Liu et al. [3] adopted LPC2294 to construct embedded hardware platform for elevator remote monitoring system. Design of interconnection gateway in elevator remote monitoring system was proposed by Zexi et al. [4]. Flores et al. [5] presented a method that uses the induction motor of the elevator system as a sensor in order to detect this kind of mechanical fault. Zeng et al. [6] presented a smart elevator door control system based on image processing technology. A real time monitoring and controlling of an elevator prototype based on PLC was developed by Irmak et al. [7].

3 IMPLEMENTATION STEPS

3.1 Model of Elevator User

Figure 2 depicts the use case model of elevator user.

Fig. 2. Use-Case Diagram of the Proposed Model

3.2 Depth Calculation

We may use normal webcams or Microsoft Kinect cameras for measuring and calculating depth information which will help us to calculate the volume taken inside the elevator. We need to find the depth information of the objects inside the elevator for that we can estimate the volume capacity of the elevator. Figure 3 shows an example of stereo image pair.

Fig. 3. Sample Snapshot for Stereoscopic Depth Estimation

Figure 4 depicts how to calculate the depth information.

Fig. 4. Calculation of the Disparity by using Two Cameras

In the Figure 4, x and x' be the distances between points in image plane corresponding to the scene point 3D and their camera center, B be the known distance between two cameras, and f be the focal length of camera. Thus it finds corresponding matches between two images. By dint of two cameras along with f and B , it is easy to find the depth information of a certain object inside the elevator.

3.3 Threshold for Volume Constraint Estimation

After estimating of necessary and sufficient parameters, the threshold for volume constraint will be estimated.

3.4 Warning to the Passengers

The user interface for the user outside the elevator, when somebody (outside) press/call the elevator there will occur two cases: (i) It will warn the user that the elevator is fully occupied and it will not stop; or (ii) It will just give the signal that there is still the space and how much space left for an object and it will stop. The user interface for the user inside the elevator, when somebody (inside) press the destination floor also two cases will occur: (i) If the elevator is not called then it will just go direct to the destination floor; or (ii) If it was called also it will get and calculate the inside volume and the same will happen as the outside scene.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Experimental Setup

Webcams are used to capture images. Using image subtraction area and volume space is calculated. If the volume is beyond the allowed space the elevator will not stop unless if it is stopped from the inside.

4.2 Most-likely Outcome

We have implemented our proposed system using a small scale setup. Outcome of our proposed system demonstrates the potential use of it in our daily life applications. The system will tolerate maximum of 10% of possible errors because we are going to use more than one camera and thus occlusion related error and noises will be reduced. The system will be installed in the elevators servers where by the servers will be controlling the elevators with the help of the cameras which will be used to calculate the depth of the objects and results into the volume of the certain object. The system will be easily accessible and inexpensive because it supports both normal webcam and Microsoft kinect camera.

4.4 Shortcomings

The proposed system was tested with a small scale implementation. It is important to find its efficacy on testing it on a large scale industrial implementation. Alternatively, any kind of simulation works would be helpful to determine its performance.

5 CONCLUSION

We addressed an automatic system that can estimate and display the free weight and volume of an elevator for the passen-

gers using sensors and computer vision techniques. Consequently, the passengers can make a decision and ride on their commodious elevators. Future study will include a large scale implementation and conduct experiment to know the performance of the proposed system a bit more.

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